

Quantum Frequency/Wavelength and the Normalization of Probability Part II

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In Part I, we noted that even though classically a $P(x)dx = Cdx/v(x)$, where $v(x)$ is defined for a bound problem with a fixed length between classical turning points used for normalization, if one considers a free particle there is no natural length. We thus suggested that there must be an internal length required for probability normalization for a free particle. We suggested that this should follow from kinematic variables which are associated with motion and chose E and p , in particular because for a photon: $x/t = E/p$ so $constant/p$ and $constant/E$ seem to possibly represent a length and time scale. We then generalized to a particle with rest mass.

Here we note, as in (1), that a fixed length required for spatial probability normalization is not consistent with a single p at each x . In other words, a probability distribution allows $constant/p$ to be resolved as a length unit. We suggested that $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability distribution and ruler generating function such that $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ which is linked to the classical $P(x)dx = dx/L$, which uses the non-natural length L . At each x , there is p and $pp/2m$ which matches the classical result, but this is at odds with the notion of a probability distribution $\exp(ipx)$. (Note: it is $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ which is similar to $P(x)$ and which demonstrates equal dt for fixed dx .)

If one examines $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$, then as argued in (1) for a notion of $constant/p$ to make sense one might expect $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ in $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ which is in fact the case. Furthermore, $d/dx \cos(px)$ starts at 0 at $x=0$ becomes negative, then 0, then rises. A similar, but shifted, behaviour occurs for $\sin(px)$. These are pieces of p multiplied by probability, not the overall $p = p \exp(ipx)/\exp(ipx)$. Nevertheless, $p \exp(ipx) = -i\hbar d/dx \exp(ipx)$ should represent some of the physical complications occurring in this nonclassical scenario. It is too simple to simply state that one has p and $pp/2m$ at each point, we argue.

We try to extend these ideas to the case of a potential $V(x)$. In particular, if one has a square well potential, this should be analogous to a particle moving freely in space. If \hbar/p defines a length in that case, then this natural, kinematics based length should also appear in the square well (despite the well having a finite length) and if in the square well, then in every potential. In such a case, each x point is linked with $p_{rms}(x)p_{rms}(x)/2m + V(x) = E_n$ (nonrelativistic), so instead of p and $pp/2m$ at each x , there is $p_{rms}(x)$ and $p_{rms}(x)p_{rms}(x)/2m$, but there should still be a $pave(x) = -i\hbar d/dx \ln W / W$, where $W = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$, at each x . This exhibits similar behaviour to $-i\hbar d/dx \cos(px)$. As a result, a natural normalization length for the notion of spatial probability leads to a length unit governed by a probability distribution with probability 0 at the endpoints and an unusual $pave(x)$. This scheme, nevertheless governs which E_n may exist which is a physical phenomenon..

Free Particle Natural Length

In Part I, we noted that $P(x)dx = Cdx/v(x)$ is introduced in the literature (see reference in Part I) for a bound problem which has a natural length, namely the distance between the classical turning points. This allows for the normalization constant to be calculated.

Such is not the case for a free particle. There is no natural length in this case and there should be no need to introduce an artificial one, i.e.

$$P(x)dx = dx/L \quad \text{where } L \text{ is an artificially introduced length ((1))}$$

We suggested that a normalization length should exist and that for a free particle it should be natural and probably follow from a kinematic variable. This led us to suggest:

$$\text{Time interval} = \text{constant}/E \quad \text{and} \quad \text{length unit} = \text{constant}/p \quad ((2))$$

We based this on a photon, i.e. $x/t = E/p$ and then generalized to a particle with rest mass.

One still has the classical notion of:

P and $p^2/2m$ nonrelativistically at each x ((3)), but at the same time a length interval given by

$\text{constant}/p$. The length interval is needed for probability normalization, but seems to be completely at odds with p constant at each x . In particular, we suggested:

$$P_1(x) = \exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px) \quad ((4))$$

For the probability (or ruler generating function), such that $\cos(px)$ has 0 values at each end of a wavelength and $\sin(px)$ also, although the x values are shifted in this case.

It is only: $\exp(ipx) \exp(-ipx) = 1$ which may be linked with ((1)). One may also add the artificial length $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ which does not change the fact that a natural one, \hbar/p also exists and has physical implications (e.g. two slit interference).

We argued in (1) that if one has a natural length, $\text{constant}/p$, there should be implications, while p , $p^2/2m$ at each x seems to indicate none. We noted in (1) that both $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ represent interference type patterns and may be written in terms of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ even though there is only an overall p at each x point. Here we suggest that the implications of $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are too important for one to only think in terms of a single p value.

We further note that if one considers: $-i \hbar d/dx \exp(ipx)$ for $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ separately, one has for $\cos(px)$ a value of 0 which becomes negative, then changes to 0 again before becoming positive. Even though there is a single p , and $-i \hbar d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$, there is more activity in p than first meets the eye. We suggest that there is important physicality to $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ for both the two-slit interference reason, but also for the bound state situation in which $\cos(px)$ remains when one adds $a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$ for $a(p)=a(-p)$. This result is supposed to be part of $W(x)$ and is not smoothed over when one calculates $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$.

Quantum Bound State

Given the natural fixed length requirement for spatial probability for a free particle, what does one do for a bound particle? In such a case, there is a natural length, namely the distance between classical turning points. The problem is that for a square well, motion is like that of a free particle in the well and if a free particle is associated with a natural probability length, $\text{constant}/p$, then so too should the particle in the square well case. If this is the situation, then this natural length should occur for any potential, as there is a physicality to this natural length. In such a case, however:

$$p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E_n \quad \text{and there is } p(x) \quad ((5))$$

In the free particle case, one had p and $pp/2$ instead.

If one has natural units of length in the bound case, they cannot be given by $\text{constant}/p$ as in the free case, yet must exist nevertheless. Furthermore ((5)) must hold, although it is not clear what is happening if a p is linked with a length $\text{constant}/p$ and $p(x)$ only holds a given x .

If one considers the free particle analogy further, then one should consider a real probability distribution over some natural length, with probability tending to 0 at the endpoints and $-i \hbar d/dx$ Probability distribution = p ave (unnormalized). Here d/dx is the translational generator.

Thus, for a real distribution with 0 at the endpoints of a piece of natural length, one has p positive, then 0, then negative, just as in the $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ pieces of the free particle $\exp(ipx)$. We further note that one natural length piece may not hold for the entire potential, unless it is a square well type.

The question then becomes: How should one create the natural length pieces such that they yield ((5))?

The clue seems to follow from the form of $V(x)$, as we have noted previously. For a free particle, $pp/2m$ is energy, but it is associated with a length, $\text{constant}/p$, not a point x . It is a contradiction then to have potential energy defined at $V(x)$. $V(x)$ must instead be a kind of average kinetic energy. An average, however, requires a probability distribution. We have suggested in previous notes that one should use the same distribution as $\exp(ipx)$, because a collision with the potential is like a free particle hitting the potential: This is the case even in Newtonian mechanics.

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((6))$$

This, however, means that average energy is formed using $\exp(ipx)$ with $pp/2m$ or:

$$KE \text{ ave} = \{ \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad pp/2m \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p)\exp(ipx) \}$$

Why does the kinetic energy have a $W = \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) \exp(ipx)$ in the denominator and the expression in ((6)) doesn't? We argue that $KE_{\text{ave}}(x)$ is used in an equation with E_n (energy). If

$p^2/2m$ is multiplied by $\exp(ipx)$, then E should also be multiplied by $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. $\psi(x) \exp(ipx)$ is also multiplied by W to allow for momentum changes, namely $\exp(ipx)\exp(ikx)$ linked to energy, V_k .

Then:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((7))$$

Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ from the free particle is very much present in the bound problem. Even though this nicely accounts for ((7)), there is still the issue of:

$$P_{ave} = -i\hbar d/dx W / W \quad \text{where } W = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((8))$$

This changing p , however exists in $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ and is of the same nature, we argue. The fixed length required for a probability distribution leads to a changing p_{ave} which is not simply a mathematical artifact, we argue.

The fixed length based on a natural conditions (not a length imposed a priori in the problem) has at least two important implications. First, only certain E_n values may exist and secondly $\int dx \psi_n(x)\psi_m(x) = 0$ if $n \neq m$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that the introduction of natural length, \hbar/p , for a free particle to allow for probability normalization is linked with strange behaviour of $-i\hbar d/dx \cos(px)$ and $-i\hbar d/dx \sin(px)$, if one uses $\exp(ipx)$ to represent the probability. In other words, the Newtonian p and $p^2/2m$ hold at each x , but at the same time there is a strange average p which starts at 0 for $\cos(px)$, becomes negative, then 0 and then positive again with a similar behaviour for $\sin(px)$. Given that $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ appear as interference patterns and lead to two slit interference, we suggest that this is not a mathematical artifact.

We consider the case of a potential $V(x)$ for which there is a natural length, that between classical turning points. Even though such a natural length exists, for a constant potential, the natural \hbar/p should still exist. We argue that if it exists in this case, it exists for all $V(x)$, only one does not have \hbar/p . Thus, the idea of a natural length seems to be fundamental, where it is given by \hbar/p or \hbar/p_{ave} or not. At the same time there is $p(x)^2/2m + V(x) = E_n$ and $p(x)$ at each x , but there should still be the unusual p behaviour given by $-i\hbar d/dx$ applied to the probability distribution associated with the natural length or length pieces which may be different. In this case, there is no one directional motion and so no two dimensions as in $\exp(ipx)$.

We argue that for a free particle $p^2/2m \exp(ipx)$ is average energy within the natural length even though energy itself is $p^2/2m$. As a result, one may formulate a $KE_{ave}(x) = \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \ p^2/2m \right\} / \left(\sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \right)$ because the denominator is multiplied by E_{total} to create an average and $V(x)$ becomes $\sum \text{over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$ to allow for single free particle collisions with the potential, an idea which holds in Newtonian mechanics. The key point is that

the natural length does not disappear and this length follows from $\exp(ipx)$ which still appears in the bound state description. This natural length has two important implications. It leads to discrete E_n and orthogonal $W_n(x)$ s.

References

1. Ruggeri,, Francesco R. Information and Quantum $\exp(ipx)$ - The Importance of X Information Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2024)